

THE ESSENCE OF COMPETITIVENESS, COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES AND COMPETITIVE STRATEGIES

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Abstract: The article discusses the concept of competition, the main features of competition, and types of competition. An analysis was carried out, positive and negative aspects were identified.

Key words: competition, methods of competition, competitors, price competition, marketing environment, microenvironment, macroenvironment.

Competition is the confrontation between economic entities in the struggle for economic resources, the process of interaction between various enterprises and organizations in order to provide their products with the best conditions for sale in the sales market by meeting the needs of consumers and achieving the main goal of any enterprise - extracting maximum profit.

The marketing system considers an organization or enterprise not as a separate entity, but in conjunction with other market entities, taking into account all relationships and information flows between economic entities.

The environment in which the organization operates, its conditions, is called the marketing environment of the enterprise. According to F. Kotler's definition, the marketing environment is a set of subjects, factors and conditions operating outside the organization and influencing the ability of the enterprise's marketing service to conduct successful cooperation with potential clients.

The marketing environment of an enterprise consists of several components:

- microenvironment;
- macro environment.

The microenvironment represents those forces that are directly related to the enterprise itself and its ability to meet customer needs. This includes suppliers, marketing intermediaries, competing organizations and businesses, and others.

The macroenvironment represents the forces of a wider range of influences that affect the microenvironment. These include demographic, economic, technical and political factors.

Thus, we can conclude that competition is an integral part of the enterprise's microenvironment and without its study and analysis it is

impossible to develop an optimal strategy for the enterprise's activities in the market. There are a large number of definitions of what competitors are. Competitors are subjects of the marketing system, and, considering this concept from this side, we can give the following definition.

Competitors are enterprises or organizations that produce the same products, or products with similar characteristics and qualities and sell them in the same market segments

The presence of competing firms gives rise to such a phenomenon in the economy as competition.

From an economic point of view, competition is a process of interaction between suppliers, individual product manufacturers, and the struggle between them for the most favorable conditions for the production and sale of products.

In other words, competition is nothing more than rivalry between individual business entities and individuals striving to achieve the same goal, namely, extracting the maximum possible profit.

In a narrower sense, competition can be characterized as the struggle of enterprises and organizations for consumer demand in the same market segments.

In these definitions, the following points are important from a marketing point of view.

1. The main idea is that there is interaction between enterprises and organizations that produce products or offer services and compete in promoting their goods to the market.

2. The struggle is for limited consumer demand. It is the fact that the demand for goods and services is limited that forces competing enterprises to fight with each other.

If we imagine that the needs of consumers were satisfied by the products of one enterprise, then other enterprises would be deprived of the opportunity to sell their products. If consumer demand is not limited, then the relationship between enterprises producing the same products could rather be called cooperation rather than competition.

3. Competition develops only in market segments accessible to enterprises. Therefore, in order to reduce the pressure of competitive factors, an enterprise can go into market segments that are inaccessible to other companies, where competition is not so strong.

Some economists divide competition, based on its methods, into:

- pricing (price competition related to the price of products sold);

- qualitative (non-price competition related to the quality of products sold).

Price-setting competition appeared in ancient times, when even identical goods were sold in markets at different prices. The only way for a merchant to attract the attention of buyers was to reduce the cost of the goods.

Currently, price-setting competition has lost its importance, and often the product manufacturer prefers non-price methods of competition. This does not mean that enterprises do not wage price wars. The bottom line is that a company can reduce the cost of its products only up to a certain limit. A further reduction in price will mean that the company will operate at a loss, that is, the funds spent on the production and sale of products will exceed the funds received from its sale. Competition in this form leads to a general deterioration in the financial condition of competing enterprises and often to ruin, so enterprises try to avoid introducing price-setting competition in an open form.

It is usually used in the following situations:

- in the struggle between small enterprises and monopolies, when enterprises have neither the means nor the ability to use non-price methods of competition;
- when an enterprise enters a new market sector or introduces new products to the market;
- when critical situations arise in the sales market and consumer demand for the company's products decreases.

There is also hidden pricing competition when an enterprise introduces new products into a market segment and sets a low price that is disproportionate to the funds spent on production of the product.

Non-price competition brings to the fore the higher consumer value of a product than its competitors (firms produce goods of higher quality, more reliable, provide a lower consumption price, and have a more modern design).

The following main areas of competitive activity of the company can be distinguished:

- 1) competition in the field of raw materials markets for gaining positions in resource markets in order to provide production with the necessary material resources, promising materials, highly qualified specialists, modern equipment and technology in order to ensure higher labor productivity than competitors;
- 2) competition in the field of sales of goods and/or services on the market;
- 3) competition between buyers in sales markets.

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